

Open Life Science

Sharing - Connecting - Empowering

Bérénice Batut (CC BY-SA 4.0)

A mentoring & training program for Open Science ambassadors

The Open Life Science (OLS) program helps **individuals and stakeholders in research** to become **Open Science ambassadors**.

About

This is a **16-week long personal mentorship and cohort-based training**, where participants (organisers, hosts, mentors and project leads/mentees) of this program will:

- share their expertise and gain knowledge essential to create, lead, and sustain an Open Science project

Applications

OLS-4 runs from September 2021 to January 2021. Applications for OLS-5 will open in late 2021 or early 2022. [Sign up to our low-traffic news list](#) to hear when OLS-5 applications open.

Timeline

- **June 21, 2021:** Call for Application opens on [Open Review](#)

See the [guidelines and templates](#)

- **June 30, 2021:** Application webinar (🗣️ Talk + ? Q&A) - 📎 [Notes with Zoom call link](#) - 📺 Recording (to be shared)

Watch recordings from previous webinars on [YouTube](#)

- **July 9, 2021:** Application Clinic Call (? Q&A) - 📎 [Notes with Zoom call link](#)

At this call, OLS team will be available to provide help if you have any question related to your application

- **July 19, 2021:** Open Review registration deadline
- **July 21, 2021:** Call for applications closed
- **August 16, 2021:** Successful applicants announced
- **September 13, 2021:** Start of the 16-week program
- **January 21, 2022:** Conclusion of the 16-week program (after a 3-weeks break end of December - beginning of January)

Have a question or need any support to join this cohort? We are here to help - feel free to email [team\[at\]openlifesci.org](mailto:team@openlifesci.org), chat in real-time on [Gitter](#) or connect on Twitter [@openlifesci](#).

individually or in teams. Project ideas can range from solving technical questions to creating an open data project or report, developing an open source software project, writing an open publication, facilitating community/team culture movements, advancing open educational resources or contributing to other existing projects/communities.

Check out the projects developed in the previous cohorts:

- [OLS-1](#) from January to April 2020, [29 participants](#) with [20 projects](#)
- [OLS-2](#) from September to December 2020, [52 participants](#) with [32 projects](#)
- [OLS-3](#) from February to May 2021, [66 participants](#) with [37 projects](#)

All applications are welcome, whether the project is just an idea at this stage or something that is running for years, but, the projects must:

- promote one or several Open Science practices (i.e. Open Access, Open Source, Citizen Science,) in life science
- state a possible measurable outcome (i.e. feature, module, or minimum viable product) from this program
- create an inclusive space and welcome contributions from their community members

You don't have a project but want to join OLS-4? Please check our [dedicated issue](#) and contact us at team@openlifesci.org.

Does OLS only accept life science projects?

Modern science and scientific communities stand in the interface of computation and other research fields. Life science is one of them. This interdisciplinary position provides an exciting opportunity for new scientists to understand and welcome open leadership practices – skills that aren't necessarily taught in the traditional education system.

OLS fills this gap by offering structured training and mentoring to help participants implement "open by design" principles in

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practitioners from this field who are experts and mentors in this program. Therefore, OLS was initially designed with life science researchers and projects in mind.

However, with the growing interest from the community members and the transferable nature of lessons learned in this program, we have expanded the scope to other fields where these skills will be directly applicable.

What's in it for you?

We want to make this program mutually beneficial for all the participants. Here are a few values we think you will receive from participating in this project.

- Become a contributing member of this community
- Collaborate with others in Open Science projects
- Exchange skills with others and build your profiles
- Highlight and promote your resources
- Gain insights from other experts in the field
- Work on short-term projects and publish online
- Get recognition and acknowledgment for your work
- Co-develop this program by sharing feedback

The program itself

To illustrate the OLS journey, we use a persona/story of Joy, a mentee participating in the program, and Sam, their mentor, as they progress through their open science training.

Joy will provide an outline of a project in their application that they will develop in the program. Additionally, they will indicate

After the selection process, they will be involved in the following steps of this program:

1. Based on their common interests, they will be introduced to each other as suitable mentee and mentor

They will meet every 2nd week on **mentee-mentor calls** (around 30 minutes). Sam will help Joy evaluate their understanding of the new topics introduced in the program, and guide their progress by providing constructive feedback. Joy will be given assignments before these calls to help them apply new skills to their project. When needed, Joy and Sam will connect with other experts to invite consultation on their project.

2. Joy will participate in online training calls and share insights with other participants in the program.

In these **cohorts calls**, they will be introduced to new topics and resources, participate in break-out discussions, and listen to expert talks.

3. Joy will get to know their peers from the cohort during social and co-working calls.

They will share their project ideas, learn about others' projects and discuss assignments.

4. A final graduation call will allow Joy to present their project to other participants and exchange values.

Sam will also participate in **mentor training** calls and attend topic-based discussions with other mentors aimed at enhancing their mentoring skills.

A self-evaluation survey, mid-cohort survey and post-cohort survey will help Joy and Sam in positioning their knowledge in open science leadership before, during and after the program.

For the next round, Joy may share what they learned by mentoring a new project in the future cohort and Sam will continue their mentoring effort or take an expert role.

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enhancement we'd love for you to [open an issue](#) on our GitHub repository because then we can get right on it.

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